

Alkaline Earth Metal Complexes of Hydroxyaromatic Ketones

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Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} complexes of the type ML₂(H₂O)₂ (where HL = 2-hydroxyacetophenone, hap or 2-hydroxypropiophenone, hpp) have been synthesised by the reactions of the metal chlorides with hydroxyaromatic ketones. These have been characterised by elemental analyses, ir, nmr and mass spectra

THE alkaline earth metal complexes of the type ML₂ with aromatic hydroxyaldehydes¹ and β-diketones² have been studied. ¹H nmr spectra of benzoyl-acetonate complexes³ and X-ray crystal structures of dibenzoylmethanates⁴ have been reported. However, the alkaline earth metal complexes of hydroxyaromatic ketones such as 2-hydroxyacetophenone and 2-hydroxypropiophenone have not been reported so far and in the present paper the synthesis and ir, nmr and mass spectra of these complexes are described.

Experimental

2-Hydroxyacetophenone (John Baker), 2-hydroxypropiophenone (Fluka) and ethanol were purified by distillation before use. MgCl₂·6H₂O (Glaxo), CaCl₂·2H₂O (E. Merck), SrCl₂·6H₂O (E. Merck) and BaCl₂·2H₂O (Glaxo) were of AR grade.

Mg^{II} and Ca^{II} complexes of 2-hydroxyacetophenone and 2-hydroxypropiophenone: To an ethanolic solution of metal chloride (~1.5 g, 8 mmol) an ethanolic solution (4 ml) of 2-hydroxyacetophenone or 2-hydroxypropiophenone was added in 1:2 molar ratio. pH of the resulting clear solution was raised to ~8.5 by adding aqueous ammonia. The solid product was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure.

Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} complexes: Sr(hap)₂(H₂O)₂ and Ba(hpp)₂(H₂O)₂ were prepared by adding ethanolic solution of the ligand to the aqueous solution of metal chloride. Sr(hpp)₂(H₂O)₂ and Ba(hap)₂(H₂O)₂ were prepared by using aqueous solution of the ligand and the metal chloride and following the similar procedure.

Mg, Ca and Sr were determined volumetrically and barium was estimated gravimetrically⁵. C and H were determined on Coleman 33 analyser. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on Varian EM-360 and EM-390 spectrometers (60 or 90 MHz) using TMS as reference at the University

of Alabama, U.S.A. Mass spectra were recorded on Kratos MS-25 (70 eV), and Kratos MS-80 RF (8 KeV) spectrometers using DS 55 data system and xenon as calibrating gas. *m*-Nitrobenzyl alcohol was used as a matrix and the peaks at *m/z* 289 and 307 were observed on account of the ions formed from the matrix.

Results and Discussion

The complexes (Table 1) are stable, yellow solids, insoluble in water and soluble in DMSO. They decompose at 220–320° except Ca(hpp)₂(H₂O)₂ which melts at 240°.

Ir spectra: The ir spectra of the complexes exhibit strong bands at 1 600–1 650 cm⁻¹, indicating the presence of the coordinated C=O groups and the strong bands at 1 500–1 550 cm⁻¹ assigned to C=C stretching. In free 2-hydroxyacetophenone and 2-hydroxypropiophenone, bands at 1 650 and 1 640 cm⁻¹ respectively have been assigned⁶ to ν_{C=O}. These bands shift to lower wavenumber side in the complexes. The weak bands at 420–470 cm⁻¹ which are absent in the free ligands may be assigned to ν_{M-O} of M–O–C bonds in the complexes. Weak bands at 220–330 cm⁻¹ may be due to M–O stretching of M–O–H bonds formed by the coordination of water molecules to the metal ion.

¹H nmr spectra: The aromatic protons of *o*-C₆H₄ group in the complexes of hydroxyacetophenone and hydroxypropiophenone are clearly resolved and exhibit triplet, doublet, triplet, doublet pattern in the region δ 6–8. The CH₃ protons of hydroxyacetophenone moiety of the complexes give a singlet at δ ~2.40 and the CH₃ and CH₂ protons of hydroxypropiophenone moiety exhibit a triplet at δ ~1.0 and a quartet at δ ~2.90 respectively. The δ values of these protons are almost the same as observed in the free ligands. These ligands exhibit a singlet at δ 12.4 ppm due to the OH proton which disappears in the complexes indicating the binding

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND ¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.*	Analyses % : Found/(Calcd.)			δ(ppm)			
		C	H	M	CH ₃	CH ₂	ArH	
1.	Mg(hap) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	58.11 (58.12)	5.49 (5.48)	7.32 (7.35)	2.10(s)	—	5.92(t), 6.82(t), 6.33(t),	6.16(d), 7.26(d), 6.56(d),
2.	Mg(hpp) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	60.15 (60.27)	6.15 (6.18)	6.79 (6.78)	1.00(t)	2.90(q)	7.22(t), 6.09(t), 7.0(t),	7.69(d), 6.42(d), 7.46(d)
3.	Ca(hap) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	55.47 (55.48)	5.24 (5.23)	11.22 (11.55)	2.40(s)	—	6.26(t), 7.05(t), 6.03(l),	6.56(d), 7.52(d), 6.39(d),
4.	Ca(hpp) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	56.96 (57.73)	5.90 (5.92)	10.69 (10.70)	1.03(t)	2.90(q)	6.95(t), 6.31(t), 7.10(t),	7.46(d), 6.53(d), 7.60(d)
5.	Sr(hap) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	48.72 (48.78)	4.62 (4.60)	22.22 (22.24)	2.40(s)	—	6.95(t), 6.31(t), 7.10(t),	6.39(d), 7.46(d), 6.53(d),
6.	Sr(hpp) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	51.85 (51.18)	5.23 (5.25)	20.89 (20.77)	1.07(t)	2.93(q)	6.31(t), 7.10(t), 7.60(d)	6.53(d), 7.60(d), 7.60(d)
7.	Ba(hap) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	44.69 (43.21)	5.10 (4.08)	30.80 (30.97)	2.52(s)	—	6.57(t), 7.32(t), 6.88(t),	6.75(d), 7.63(d), 6.97(d),
8.	Ba(hpp) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	45.80 (45.83)	4.71 (4.70)	29.12 (29.11)	1.00(s)	3.11(q)	6.88(t), 7.51(t),	6.97(d), 7.86(d)

*hap=2-hydroxyacetophenone, hpp=2-hydroxypropiophenone.

of the metal atom to the phenolic oxygen of the ligand.

Mass spectra: Ca(hpp)₂ exhibits quite intense molecular ion peak (100%), whereas the peak of Mg(hpp)₂ is of low intensity (11.7%). In Mg(hap)₂, no molecular ion peak appears, which may be due to the thermal decomposition of the compound before it entered the ionisation chamber.

It is interesting to note that most of the complexes exhibit several peaks due to the ions formed from oligomeric species. Such oligomeric species have been previously noted in related mixed ligand complexes of magnesium⁷. Ions derived from dimeric species exhibit peaks at *m/z* 644 (2.8%) due to Mg₂(hpp)₄⁺ and at *m/z* 715 (676+K⁺; 19.6%) due to Ca₂(hpp)₄⁺.

All the complexes exhibit peaks due to M₂L₃⁺ species. Peaks at *m/z* 453 (3.2%) and 527 (27.6%) have been observed due to Mg₂(hap)₃⁺ and Ca₂(hpp)₃⁺ respectively. In some cases peaks due to such oligomeric ions are most abundant, for example, *m/z* 495 (100%) due to Mg₂(hpp)₃⁺. In the mass spectra of calcium and strontium acetylacetonates the base peaks at *m/z* 377 and 473 have been reported^{8,9} to be due to Ca₂(acac)₃⁺ and Sr₂(acac)₃⁺ respectively. However, in case of magnesium acetylacetonate the peak at *m/z* 345 due to Mg₂(acac)₃⁺ ion is only of 10% intensity as observed by Macdonald and Shannon⁹.

Peaks corresponding to the ions resulting from the higher polymeric species have also been observed. In the mass spectrum of Mg(hpp)₂ a peak due to Mg₃(hpp)₄⁺ species is obtained at *m/z* 669 (668+H⁺, 14%). Ca(hpp)₂ exhibits a peak at *m/z* 865 (11.5%) due to Ca₃(hpp)₅⁺ species. A quite intense peak at *m/z* 378 (22.2%) is observed due to Ca₂(hpp)₂⁺. Macklin and Dudek⁸ observed peaks due to M₃L₅⁺ and M₄L₇⁺ ions in case of acetylacetonates of Ca and Sr (*m/z* 615 Ca₃(acac)₅⁺, 853 Ca₄(acac)₇⁺ and 1045

Sr₄(acac)₇⁺). Formation of various oligomeric species can be explained with the help of the following ion-molecule aggregation reactions: ML₂⁺ → ML⁺ + L; ML⁺ + ML⁺ → M₂L₂⁺; M₂L₂⁺ + L → M₂L₃⁺; ML₂⁺ + ML⁺ → M₂L₃⁺; M₂L₃⁺ + L → M₂L₄⁺; M₂L₃⁺ + ML⁺ → M₃L₄⁺; M₃L₄⁺ + L → M₃L₅⁺.

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